

Timescales of transgressive teaching in social justice mathematics

Susan Staats, University of Minnesota, staats@umn.edu

Lori Ann Laster, University of Minnesota

This project presentation reports on a conversation amongst in-service secondary mathematics teachers who had just participated in a social justice mathematics professional development session. As they discussed how they might incorporate the social justice activity into their classes, their conversation invoked a wide range of timescales. Timescales, as presented by Lemke, are categories of actions that are somewhat predictable, periodic and that either constrain or enact agency. Collectively, the teachers mentioned 20 timescales that imagine forms of agency that unfold over a range of time frames, from a moment to nearly a century. Timescale analysis of this conversation reveals the intensively hegemonic conditions which teachers must consider when preparing to teach transgressively.

Introduction

This paper analyses a conversation amongst several experienced, in-service secondary mathematics teachers sharing their thinking about how one should teach a social justice mathematics activity. The teachers had just participated in a professional development presentation of a mathematics activity on gender inclusivity that would require them to explain concepts of transgender identity and gender-neutral forms of speaking (Whipple, Staats, & Harrison, 2020). During a subsequent focus group interview on attitudes towards equity teaching, two teachers, one with a progressive and the other with a conservative political stance, commented that they had particularly enjoyed the presentation and wanted to present it in their class. However, their initial thinking about how to do this was divergent, and created a lively argument about how one should teach social justice mathematics topics. The conservative teacher described in detail techniques of maintaining mathematical neutrality. The progressive teacher emphasized alliance with a university professional development program as a technique for teaching as she wished to teach.

While imagining themselves teaching a topic that would be received as controversial by some school stakeholders, teachers mentioned an extreme range of timescales. Timescales are activities or processes that unfold over a relatively predictable period of time and that repeat periodically, such as the time it takes to complete a routine calculation, teaching over a class day or year, using a particular textbook or curriculum for several years, and so on

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(Lemke, 2000). Timescales are sometimes hierarchical. For example, a yearlong curriculum might influence the activities in class each day, and each day in class might be composed of multiple cycles of routine calculation, or components of inquiry learning, or other repeated activities specified by the curriculum. After some years, a new curriculum might be adopted with new nested cycles of activities.

Timescales can be seen as modes of action, but also, because they are somewhat predictable, speakers can also refer to them or invoke them in a conversation. Referring to a timescale can be a socially powerful act, a speaker's bid to frame the relevant scope or basis of interpretation for the ensuing conversation. This project presentation treats references to timescales as a way to understand teachers' imagination of the landscape of power that surrounds them should they embark upon teaching social justice mathematics.

Timescales and agency

Discourse analysis using timescales requires attention to the ways in which forms of linguistic referencing specify elements of context — near or far in space or in time — and thereby establish the “scope of understandability” (Blommaert et al., 2015, p. 119). In mathematics education research, timescales have been used to clarify details of positioning theory (Herbel-Eisenmann, Wagner, Johnson, Suh, & Figueras, 2015); propose new, multilevel research methods (Noyes, 2013); and to understand processes of linguistically-mediated social stratification (Barwell, 2020).

Timescales invoke agency because they imply particular types of action carried out over a stretch of time, forms of agency that are somewhat predictable by virtue of being periodic, but never fully so. The hierarchical nature of timescales requires consideration of how different kinds of agencies relate to each other. Timescale analysis is interested in the interplay of agentic constraint, because longer duration timescales such as adopted curriculum tend to require particular kinds of actions at shorter timescales. However, actions at shorter timescales are the constituents of longer timescales, and through this, disruptive agency to change is always possible (Lemke, 2000). For example, what a teacher talks about in one class day might be partly constrained or formatted by the curriculum chosen by the school for use over several years. However, if the curriculum does not allow teachers to teach, and to speak, as they wish, these shorter timescales might provoke teachers to take action towards changing the curriculum. In this way, timescale analysis can give insight into teachers' experiences of power, and potentially, into their means of enacting power in their educational system.

Methods of timescale analysis

Although the timescale construct has been productively critiqued as being less-well-defined than Lemke's 2000 presentation might suggest (Blommaert et al., 2015), here, timescales usefully describe the political range and intensity of the teachers' conversation. For teachers from different schools to share teaching perspectives, they need to refer to situations that

are widely-experienced and that have partly-predictable responses. Teachers need to discuss the “scopes of understandability” of predictable events across school stakeholders. In this paper, we focus on identifying references to timescales in the conversation as a way to describe teachers’ envisioning of the power dimensions of their work. A later paper will analyse the interactional processes of scale-jumping through which participants enacted power over each other during the emergent conversation (Barwell, 2020).

For this project, each sentence in each conversational turn was analysed for any reference to a social, physical or historical event that predictably repeats over some period of time. Shorter scale examples include how one should speak in class during a politically situated mathematics activity and how students, school administrators, and families might respond. Middle scale examples included references to political protests that were increasingly frequent at the time of the conversation in 2017, such as high-profile athletes’ Black Lives Matter protests, the increasingly public presence of White supremacist racism and anti-Semitism, and student-led school activism towards gender diversity. Longer scale examples included references to the United States’ periodic military actions so that a student’s response to a social justice mathematics lesson might be conditioned by their relationships with multiple generations of military veterans in their families. We arranged these timescales in a roughly hierarchical manner in terms of the duration, that is, the time it takes to complete the process. Due to space constraints, only some of the 20 timescales are given in Table 1.

Timescale	Approximate duration
Multiple generations in a family: References to Brother, Dad, and Grandpa	Eight decades
The family life cycle: The 14-17 years it takes to raise a child to near-adulthood	1.5 decades
Passage into middle age	A decade
The cycle of the U.S. going to war periodically	Every few years
Types of contemporary political protest in the U.S.: Black Lives Matter; footballers protesting the National Anthem; right-wing marches	Monthly or weekly
The academic year shared by a teacher and a class of students	A year
Getting a pay check from your school	Every two weeks
Students’ political expression during a day at school	A day
School administration, parental, community responses to student political expression	A day
Teaching a topic in a class	An hour
Introduce a conversational topic	A moment
Choose a response to a conversational topic	A moment

Table 1: Timescales relevant to social justice mathematics teaching.

Conclusion

Timescales mattered greatly to these teachers as they described how they might teach a social justice mathematics activity. As Table 1 indicates, teachers' discussion of whether mathematics should be, can be or must be taught neutrally was permeated with references to the periodic events from daily school routines, from the communities that the schools serve, and from contemporary and historical political actions. Analysis of this conversation suggests that as teachers consider transgressive teaching, they weigh matters of dramatically wide scale and scope: how to choose one's words, how hold one's face, how to maintain employment, how to respond to the spectrum of current political activism, how to address the displeasure of a family implicated in nearly a century of U.S. military action. The conservative teacher's vision of teaching in a neutral manner references timescales across a tightly regimented hegemonic system that strongly resists change. All the teachers in this conversation seemed to acknowledge that Table 1 lists a range of issues that they might need to address with local stakeholders when teaching social justice mathematics.

Future effective professional development towards social justice mathematics teaching may need to spend substantial time on uncovering these concerns, analysing with teachers which timescales afford them greater agency, and how to build discursive skill in re-framing discussions regarding the broader timescales. Beyond learning to teach a social justice mathematics lesson, with its associated techniques of engaging students' mathematical learning and socio-political consciousness, teachers may need explicit preparation to enact and protect their agency across a range of temporal events far beyond the classroom.

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